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Research Article

**EFFICACY OF CT GUIDED NEEDLE BIOPSIES FOR
INTRATHORACIC MASSES BY VARIOUS METHODS**¹Dr Muhammad Touqeer Qasim, ²Dr Muhammad Zaeem, ³Dr Roba Asif¹Nishtar Medical University, Multan., ²Rawalpindi Medical University, Rawalpindi, ³Bahria University, Rawal Institute of Health Sciences, Islamabad.**Article Received:** March 2020**Accepted:** April 2020**Published:** May 2020**Abstract:**

Aim: To report our experience with computed tomography (CT)-guided coaxial needle biopsy of intra-thoracic lesions by different approaches.

Place and Duration: In the Radiology department of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020.

Material and Methods: Medical records of 100 patients who underwent a thoracic biopsy were reviewed retrospectively. Coaxial needle technique was used in all patients; A 18-gauge needle was used for transdermal penetration, and a thin needle was passed through the 22-gauge needle for aspiration. A core-needle biopsy was performed on five patients by placing 20-gauge needles coaxially. Medical records were reviewed to determine the size and location of the lesion, needle trajectory, and number of needle penetrations, causes of failure, biopsy results, and complications.

Results: The trans-sternal approach was used in mediastinal (n = 32) or intrapulmonary (n = 5) lesions. Extrapleural access to the mediastinal lesions was achieved in all but one patient in whom the 22-gauge needle traversed the lung.

Conclusion: CT-guided coaxial core-needle biopsy ensures safe access to masses in various parts of the chest and anteroposterior lung.

Keywords: Needle biopsy, computed tomography, Intrathoracic.

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INTRODUCTION:

Imaging-guided percutaneous core-needle biopsy has become the modality of choice for diagnosing intrathoracic masses. The parasternal, suprasternal, and transpulmonary approaches have been the traditional routes for the intrathoracic lesions. The extrapulmonary approach with the help of computed tomography (CT) or ultrasound (US) is best suited for lesions extending to the chest wall in front of the sternum. Most intra-chest injuries require a transpulmonary approach under CT guidelines. The transsternal approach for intrathoracic biopsy has been described in a few series of patients; the major advantage of this route is the reduction of the risks of pneumothorax and accidental injury to the internal mammary vessels. Some patients have described transthoracic biopsy approaches to the chest; the main advantage of this method is to reduce the risk of pneumothorax and accidental damage to internal nipples. The purpose of our study was to report our experience with CT-guided coaxial needle biopsy of intra-thoracic lesions by using different approaches.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This study was held in the Radiology department of Jinnah Hospital Lahore for one year duration from March 2019 to March 2020. We retrospectively evaluated the records of 100 patients (70 men, 30 women; age range, 40-60 yrs; mean age, 55 years) who had intrathoracic masses and underwent successful (n = 95) or attempted (n = 5) CT-guided percutaneous needle biopsy. To exclude bleeding diathesis, all patients had coagulation parameters and platelet counts. Written informed consent was obtained from all patients, and all biopsies were performed after continuous pulse oximetry and non-invasive blood pressure monitoring as well as conscious sedation and local anesthesia. All biopsies were performed using a helical CT scanner. Patients initially underwent imaging in the supine position with

a section thickness of 5, 7, or 10mm. Non-enhanced CT was used in 35 procedures, while two patients underwent contrast CT after intravenous administration of Urografin to identify large vessels around the lesions. All biopsies were performed using a coaxial needle biopsy technique. A variety of guide needles were used an 18-gauge needle 18-gauge Chiba needle. Needle alignment was assessed by CT and corrected if necessary. One to four passes were required for each patient. Additional spinal needle biopsies were also performed on five patients at the recommendation of a cytopathologist who examined the slides when several aspiration samples did not produce the appropriate diagnostic material. Computed tomography scans were not routinely obtained to assess complications. Expiratory chest radiographs were asked. Patients were observed 1-3 hours after surgery to ensure haemodynamic stability and respiratory monitoring.

RESULTS:

The transsternal approach was used for biopsies in the mediastinal masses or nodes (n = 52) or in intrapulmonary lesions (n = 5). The pulmonary masses were in the antero-lower part of the right (n = 30) or left (n = 14) lung, adhering and / or attacking the mediastinum or interstitial tissue, soft tissue or both. The biopsy lesions had a maximum diameter of 1-8 cm (mean 2.8 cm). Four patients adhered to the posterior surface of the sternum.

1. Squamous cell CA-12
2. Adeno-carcinoma-10
3. Large cell CA-6
4. Inflammatory-16
5. Non-Hodgkins lymphoma-11
6. Squamous bundle+Neurofibroma-4
7. Invasive-CA of Breast-1
8. Collapsed lung tissue-02
9. Infected Hydatid cyst-3

DISCUSSION:

Transsternal needle biopsy, initially performed using fluoroscopy, is now performed using CT and US, because these methods allow accurate placement and documentation of the biopsy needle and target lesion.

Mediastinal and trans-mediastinal biopsy under CT control also has its limitations and risks. The parallel approach involves a small but clear risk of bleeding due to internal trauma to the breast, as defined in CT, it may not be possible to find a safe window between

the vessels and the sternum. Therefore, most mediastinal tumors require an angular transpulmonary approach with a needle passing through the lungs, as well as changes in other mediastinal compartments and in the anterior and medial lung directions. Thanks to this technique, safe extrapulmonary access to the medial or posterior mediastinal masses behind large vessels can be obtained in the tracheal compartments or in the aortopulmonary valve. The percutaneous approach prevents the movement of ventilated lungs, thus reducing the risk of pneumothorax. In our study, pneumothorax did not develop in any of the patients with lung lesions and percutaneous biopsies. High contrast CT during biopsy suggests that precise needle path planning requires an intravenous contrast agent to help identify the mediastinal vessels. CT alone without contrast is sufficient for safe biopsy planning in most contrast patients prior to diagnosis. IT has improved. The risk of pneumothorax reported with this approach ranges from 11% to 19.2%. It is important to do IT to verify the needle direction in the small steps of the guide. We have found that percutaneous needle placement after local anesthesia and intravenous sedation is a well-tolerated safe procedure. No complications were directly related to the transthoracic approach in patients in our study. Bleeding, which is a possible complication of mediastinal biopsy, can be prevented by carefully planning the path of the biopsy needle according to the location of the large vessels, depending on the injury.

CONCLUSION:

We have found that fine needle aspiration biopsy provides sufficient tissue for diagnosis in most patients. As a result, the coaxial transsternal biopsy technique allows secure access to masses in various parts of the mediastinum and anteroposterior lung. This approach does not limit the biopsy only to the anterior mediastinum, but allows you to sample lesions in the posterior mediastinum. Routine biopsy needles can be used to penetrate the sternum and access to the mediastinum, allowing both fine needle aspiration and potential spinal sampling.

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